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Simultaneous Resolution of Clopidogrel Bisulphate and Aspirin in their Combined Dosage Form by Ratio First Derivative Spectrophotometry

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ABSTRACT

In the present work, the ratio spectra first derivative spectrophotometry is proposed for the resolution of Clopidogrel bisulphate (CLP) and Aspirin (ASP) in synthetic mixtures prepared in random fashion and tablets available in 1:1 and 1:2 ratio. The calibration graph follows Beer's law in the range of 6 to 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for clopidogrel bisulphate and from 4-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for aspirin. The mean recoveries & relative standard deviations were found as 99.40% & 0.442% for CLP and 100.09% and 0.905% for ASP, respectively in 1:1 ratio. Similarly the mean recoveries & relative standard deviations were found as 99.84% & 1.024% for CLP and 99.95% and 0.578% for ASP, respectively in 1:2 ratio. The graphical treatment of the overlapping spectra depends on division of the absorption spectrum of the binary mixture by a standard spectrum of one of the components and then calculating the first derivative of the ratio spectrum. These approaches were successfully applied to quantify CLP combined with ASP in tablets respectively and validated accordingly for random ratios in synthetic mixtures.

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INTRODUCTION

Clopidogrel bisulphate (CLP), [S-(a)(2-chlorophenyl)-6,7-dihydrothieno (3,2-C)-pyridine-5(4H) acetic acid methyl ester sulphate]¹ is a selective and irreversible inhibitor of ADP induced platelet aggregation. Aspirin (ASP), acetyl salicylic acid² is a non steroidal anti inflammatory drug having analgesic and antipyretic activity with an effective inhibition of platelet aggregation. CLP has been marketed in combination with ASP in tablets in 1:1 & 1:2 . The mixture of these compounds has commonly been used as an antiplatelet agent. ASP is a well studied drug, official in all the pharmacopoeias whereas CLP is not official in any of these pharmacopoeias³⁻⁵. Several methods appear in the literature for the simultaneous determination of CLP and ASP in their binary mixture based on spectrophotometry⁶⁻⁸, HPLC⁹⁻¹¹, and HPTLC¹². To our knowledge there is no official method for the simultaneous determination of these drugs in any pharmacopoeia. The resolution of binary mixtures of compounds with overlapped spectra by derivative technique is frequently made on the basis of zero crossing measurements. However the zero order derivative technique cannot be satisfactorily performed because of the large overlap of the absorption spectra as is occurring in the case of CLP and ASP. (Figure1).Hence a ratio spectra first derivative spectrophotometric procedure has been developed for its better resolution.

The aim of present study was to demonstrate the capability of the ratio spectra derivative spectrophotometric method to resolve and overcome the problem of overlapping spectral bands and allow the simultaneous determination of CLP and ASP without any chemical separation.

Figure 1

Overlain spectra of CLP, ASP and their binary mixture.

Figure 2a

Ratio spectra of CLP

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus

A Shimadzu 1700PC double beam spectrophotometer with a fixed slit width (1nm) was used coupled with shimadzu UVPC software.

Figure 2b Ratio first derivative spectra of CLP

Figure 3a

Ratio spectra of ASP

Figure 3b

Ratio first derivative spectra of ASP

Reagents and Chemicals

CLP and ASP were kindly supplied as gift samples by Zydus Cadila (Ahmedabad, India) and were used as received. Analytical grade methanol was used as a solvent.

Standard solutions

Stock solution of 1mg/1ml CLP and ASP were prepared separately in methanol. The standard series of the solutions containing 6-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ CLP and 4-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were prepared from the stock solutions for obtaining calibration graphs and spectra. All the solutions were prepared freshly.

Commercial tablet formulation

The quantitative assay of the commercial pharmaceutical formulations Deplatt A75 containing 75mg CLP and 75mg ASP (1:1) respectively and Deplatt A150 containing CLP 75mg and ASP150mg (1:2) (manufactured by Torrent Pharmaceuticals Ltd, India) were carried out using the developed methods.

Sample solution

Twenty tablets were accurately weighed and powdered in a mortar. An accurately weighed amount equivalent to one tablet was dissolved in methanol in a 100ml calibrated volumetric flask. After 30minutes of mechanical shaking the solution was filtered through whattman no.42 filter paper. Appropriate dilutions were prepared in methanol taking suitable aliquots of the clear filtrates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the overlain zero order spectra of CLOP and ASP and their mixture in methanol. It can be seen that the absorption spectra of CLOP and ASP are extensively overlapped and as a result the determination of these two compounds is not possible for reliable direct absorbance measurement. The main disadvantage of zero crossing derivative spectrophotometry method for resolution of binary mixture is that the selection of analytical wavelengths is critical due to very small distance between them and the values obtained are also small. Hence ratio derivative spectrophotometric method can be suitable to obviate this problem. The method allows for selection of defined analytical wavelengths of highest value due to presence of lot of maxima and minima. Hence the method offers a potential greater sensitivity and accuracy.

Optimization of parameters¹³⁻¹⁴ To optimize the simultaneous determination of CLP and ASP by using ratio spectra derivative spectrophotometric method, it is necessary to test the influence of the variables like:

1. Effect of standard divisor concentration.

In a preliminary investigation, for selecting the standard solution as divisor, appropriate concentration of CLP and ASP in the range 6-30µg/ml and 4-20µg/ml were tested respectively. Stored spectra of standard Clopidogrel solutions were divided wavelength by wavelength by a standard spectra of ASP (4-20µg/ml) Table 1. Then the first derivative of above ratio spectra were recorded and the values of the derivatives were measured at suitably selected wavelengths and plotting against the corresponding concentration to obtain the calibration graph. The similar procedure was followed for the different concentration of ASP when CLP (6-30µg/ml) was used as divisor in the same way as described above. Table 2. The calibration curve was obtained by plotting absorbance versus drug concentration. Thus a concentration of 6µg/ml of CLP and 12µg/ml of ASP as divisor gave best results in terms of signal to noise ratio and highest correlation coefficient values, being an indication of the quality of fitting of the data to the straight line.

2. Effects of derivative intervals ($\Delta\lambda$) on derivative ratio spectra.

$\Delta\lambda$, the width of the boundaries over which the derivative is calculated was tested for $\Delta\lambda=2\text{nm}$, 4nm and 8nm . The value of $\Delta\lambda=4\text{nm}$ was found optimal in connection with both slit width and wavelength interval. Thus the absorption spectra of

CLP for the solution in methanol were divided by the spectrum of the standard solution of $12\ \mu\text{g/ml}$ of ASP in the same solvent (Figure.2a) and the first derivative was plotted with the interval of $\Delta\lambda=4\ \text{nm}$. (Figure2b). It was found that the first derivative amplitudes at $242.4\ \text{nm}$ and $254.2\ \text{nm}$ were suitable for the determination of CLP in binary mixture with ASP. In similar way, the stored spectra of ASP were divided wavelength by wavelength, by $6\ \mu\text{g/ml}$ of CLP (Figure 3a).

Table 1

Optimization of divisor concentration for Clopidogrel Bisulphate.

Compound	Divisor Conc.	$\lambda(\text{nm})$	R^2
Clopidogrel Bisulphate (6-30µg/ml)	4A	241.8nm	0.9819
	8A	242.6nm	0.9989
	12A	242.4nm	0.9999
	16A	242.3nm	0.9998
	20A	242.4nm	0.9320

Table 2

Optimization of divisor concentration for Aspirin.

Compound	Divisor Conc.	$\lambda(\text{nm})$	R^2
Aspirin (4-20µg/ml)	6C	271.5nm	0.9998
	12C	271.8nm	0.9992
	18C	271.5nm	0.9996
	24C	271.8nm	0.9878
	30C	271.5nm	0.9987

First derivative was plotted with the interval of $\Delta\lambda=4\ \text{nm}$ (Figure 3b). It was found that the first derivative amplitude at $271.5\ \text{nm}$ was suitable for the determination of ASP in binary mixture with CLP. Once the optimum working condition was established,

calibration graphs were obtained at 242.4 nm and 254.2 nm for Clopidogrel bisulphate and 271.5 nm for

Table 3

Analytical data of the calibration graphs for the determination of Clopidogrel bisulphate and Aspirin.

Parameters	Clopidogrel Bisulphate		Aspirin
Wavelength (nm)	242.4	254.2	271.5
Beer's Law limit (µg/ml)	6-30	6-30	4-20
LOD (µg/ml)	0.494	0.541	0.065
LOQ (µg/ml)	1.659	1.807	0.084
Intercept	0.009	0.075	0.0574
Slope	0.072	0.092	0.1153
Correlation coefficient	0.9999	0.9996	0.9998

Table 4

Replicate determinations of synthetic mixtures of CLP and ASP analysis of tablets

CLP	ASP	Amount found µg/ml		% Recovery	
		CLP	ASP	CLP	ASP
9	12	8.93	11.87	99.22	98.91
9	14	8.90	13.91	98.88	99.35
9	16	9.10	15.95	101.11	99.68
9	18	8.98	17.73	99.77	98.56
9	20	9.05	20.04	100.55	100.20
	Mean recovery			99.90	99.34
	%RSD			0.923	0.646
6	18	5.75	17.92	99.01	99.55
9	18	8.88	17.99	98.66	99.94
12	18	11.98	17.66	99.83	98.11
15	18	14.86	17.78	99.06	98.77
18	18	18.06	18.00	100.40	100.55
	Mean recovery			99.39	98.61
	%RSD			0.711	0.974

Aspirin in the standard binary mixture and showed that the proposed method is applicable over the ranges 6-30 µg/ml for CLOP and 4-20 µg/ml for ASP. The characteristic parameters of the regression equations with LOD and LOQ are compiled in Table 3.

To determine the validity and applicability of the developed method, recovery studies¹³⁻¹⁸ were

performed in the synthetic mixtures of CLP and ASP with different ratios. Mean recoveries and %RSD were calculated. (Table 4)

Analysis of tablets

The obtained results for the synthetic mixtures were found to be satisfactory. Thus the proposed method was applied for performing the simultaneous

analysis of CLP and ASP in pharmaceutical dosage form without any chemical separation. (Table 5)

Table 5

Results obtained for marketed formulations

Formula tion	Dr ug	Label led claim (mg/t ab)	Amo unt found (mg)	%Reco very SD*	± SD
Deplatt A75	CL P	75	74.55	99.40 ± 0.79	0.44 2
	AS P			75.07	100.09 ± 0.84
Deplatt A150	CL P	75	74.88	99.84 ± 0.75	1.02 4
	AS P			150 2	149.9 51

*Average reading for five determinations.

CONCLUSION

In our study, ratio spectra first derivative was applied for the simultaneous analysis of the binary mixtures and a commercial tablet formulation containing CLP and ASP. Although the individual spectra of CLP and ASP overlap in the 200-300 nm wavelength ranges, the proposed method gave successful results for the quantitative determination of the two-component mixtures and commercial tablet formulation consisting of these two compounds. This can be considered as an advantage of the investigated methods over alternative methods for the quantitative resolution of the two-component mixtures. The proposed method described in this paper does not require any time-

consuming separation or sample preparation steps. The result of the proposed method was found to be very close to the labelled value of commercial pharmaceutical formulation. The procedure is fast and specific and works without solving equations or separation steps. Thus the developed methods can be strongly applied to a routine analysis, quality control of binary mixtures, and commercial products containing these two drugs.

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